

Durga Puja Beyond Borders

Developed by: x

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Keywords

Culture, Durga Puja, Event Management, History, Indian festival culture, Intercultural Communication, Migration, South Asian Studies

Figure 1. Screenshot from *Durga Puja Beyond Borders* (Z. Zeiler; Flying Robot Studios). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

Introduction

The educational video game *Durga Puja Beyond Borders* (see Figure 1) introduces Indian festival culture by focusing on Durga Puja. Today, Durga Puja is not only widely celebrated in India but is also a significant event for global Indian communities (e.g., Guha-Thakurta, 2015; Zeiler, 2025). The game draws on aspects of management games to playfully yet educationally introduce various layers of Durga Puja festival culture, including joint Durga Puja organizations and, especially, celebrations. It conveys educational content about the festival's history and past and present ways of worshipping and jointly celebrating, in India and beyond. Moreover, it allows a glimpse into how festivals are important events and locations for migrant communities to live and negotiate identity, heritage, and culture. This game invites players to

join the festival in an exemplary global Indian community, in the so-called Indian diaspora, in Helsinki, Finland. In *Durga Puja Beyond Borders*, you play as Laura, who takes part in organizing and celebrating a Durga Puja event hosted by a local Indian community.

The game is part of a set of two educational video games at the festival, developed specifically for university teaching. The *Durga Puja Mystery* (2020) and *Durga Puja Beyond Borders* (2021) can be played in combination or as stand-alone games, depending on the player's interest.

Facts

Release date:	2021
Developer:	collaboration between Xenia Zeiler, University of Helsinki, Finland, and Satyajit Chakrabarti, Flying Robot Studios, Kolkata, India
Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	Single player
Format:	Asynchronous
Time frame:	60–90 min, depending on the options the player chooses
Languages:	English
Environment:	Android phones and tablets; Windows PCs and laptops
Material:	The game is downloadable from the Google Play Store or via a direct link upon request; a public website additionally offers game-accompanying academic context information on the festival Durga Puja (two academic lectures, one academic blog post, and one documentary), produced specifically for the two educational video games on Durga Puja, see https://blogs.helsinki.fi/durgapuja-the-videogame/
Price:	Fully open access and free of charge, as the game development was funded by the University of Helsinki

Resonance & Criticism

Durga Puja Beyond Borders was developed for university-level humanities teaching but is open to play for anyone interested in Indian festival cultures. Collected voluntary student feedback praised the game's innovative, playful approach to learning about the festival. Additionally, the game has gained international awareness among university teachers.

Sample course titles in which the game has been used so far include “Globalization, Global Communities, and Transcultural Encounters”, “Who has got the Power? Communicating and Negotiating Authority and Identity in Indian Festival Cultures,” and “Identities and Digital Networks of Migrant Communities”.

Game Principle & Process

As mentioned above, Durga Puja Beyond Borders is an educational video game developed to introduce selected core aspects of Indian culture and society, using the festival as a content example. It focuses on the festival's celebration in Indian communities beyond India.

The player character Laura lives in Helsinki, Finland. Invited by her friend Shreya, she joins a video conference of a local Indian Durga Puja Committee as they begin preparing the annual event. The committee appoints Laura as the assistant to the group's chair, Shreya, who, in turn, mentors Laura on the festival's history and on past and present rituals and worship, iconography, mythology, and geographical travels in India and beyond.

This mentor conversation (accessible via the 'Ask Mentor' button) contains essential information that enables the player to answer quiz questions later in the game. Laura then proceeds to the 'Schedule' level, which lists the event's rituals, cultural performances, meals, and other main happenings. Using the scheduler menu that provides contact details for all committee members and a selection of vendors, the player assigns each event point to a responsible person.

Next, the player joins the actual festival celebrations, which last three days. This game level takes place in a community hall, shown in an isometric view. The player can now walk through the venue, starting conversations with visitors or just exploring. This level's main feature is the player's conversations with Durga Puja visitors (community members and friends), which offer ample opportunities for knowledge exchange. These conversations also include quiz questions that test the player's knowledge and determine the final score.

This game builds on the (at times contested) claim that educational video games add value to teaching by facilitating immersive (e.g., McMahan, 2003) and embodied (e.g., Gregersen, 2011; Lankoski, 2016; van 't Riet et al., 2018) experiences.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

Durga Puja Beyond Borders, like its predecessor, The Durga Puja Mystery, has an overall objective as well as more specific and detailed learning objectives. The primary, overarching goal is to give students and interested general audiences access to knowledge of the Durga Puja festival, particularly as celebrated beyond India, in a playful yet academically sound way. The game's sub-goals include specific usability in classroom settings across a variety of courses suited to the academic disciplines of South Asian studies, Asian studies, religious studies, and area and cultural studies.

The festival of Durga Puja has traveled widely with Indian communities, beyond many geographical and cultural borders. Today, the festival is celebrated in many places around the globe that have become home to Indian migrant communities. This game invites you to join the festival in an exemplary global Indian community, in the so-called Indian diaspora, in Helsinki, Finland. To achieve this, the game uses several pedagogical gamified features that

allow the player to join a Durga Puja event from the planning stage through the actual celebrations. This is achieved through enabling the player to converse with the planning committee in video team meetings, take support from a mentor, schedule the event plan for the celebrations and assign responsibilities, use video calls to talk with the festival planning committee members, have conversations with members of the community about Durga Puja in India and beyond, and use a library to get suggestions for further readings – all during the gameplay. Upon successful completion of all events during the three celebration days, the player receives a score based on their answers to the quiz questions throughout the game.

Durga Puja Beyond Borders is easy to use on a Windows PC or laptop with the required system requirements (<https://blogs.helsinki.fi/durgapuja-the-videogame/play/>). All practical instructions, as well as game-accompanying academic content context that can support both the teacher in content preparation and the player during gameplay, are free of charge and easily accessible. This reflects the fact that using an educational video game in classroom settings should always be supported by other learning activities, such as assigned academic readings on the game's content matter, group discussions, and the use of different media formats. As this is a single-player game, it is even more advisable to embed it in collaborative class discussions and in further information sources and learning activities on the theme.

Effectiveness

A postmortem of the game by Zeiler & Chakraborti (2024) further investigated the pros and cons, including the effectiveness. This student feedback confirms that the game supported the learning process, mainly by providing more direct and immersive access to certain festival elements than is possible in conservative learning environments (e.g., Blumberg & Blumberg, 2014; Mayer, 2014). These festival elements include, for example, audio (such as ritual and festive music) and visuals (such as colors). It has also proven effective to choose the management game genre, as it aligns with Durga Puja Beyond Borders's focus on event planning and execution.

Connecting the two games via the main player character, Laura, proved effective. Having participated in a Kolkata Durga Puja in *The Durga Puja Mystery* (2020), Laura is now interested in seeing the festival in her hometown, Helsinki. Thus, the narrative and the player character Laura may be seen as both a direct successor to *The Durga Puja Mystery* and a stand-alone game. Both games can be played in succession (with a recommendation to play *The Durga Puja Mystery* first) or independently. The fact that both games are, nevertheless, very different in terms of platform (PC and mobile), genre (mystery and management), aesthetics, soundscapes, etc., further supports reaching various player/learner types.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

The game is not yet available for iPhone. An Apple version is planned, but is subject to funding.

Reviewer(s): Johansen Quijano

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